

INTEGRATIVE DIAGNOSTICS: ROLE OF LABORATORY MEDICINE

Plebani Mario

Honorary Professor of Clinical Biochemistry and Clinical Molecular Biology, University of Padova, Italy
Adjunct Professor, Department of Pathology, University of Texas, Medical Branch, Galveston - USA

mario.plebani@unipd.it

Recent progress in diagnostic testing has the potential to enable more accurate diagnosis and improved clinical outcomes. However, diagnostic data are fragmented, being produced and delivered within the “silo” of each diagnostic discipline, and the electronic health record does little to synthesize existing data to be translated in actionable information. Therefore, despite great promise, diagnoses may still be incorrect, delayed, or never made. Integrated diagnostics (ID) represents a vision for the future, wherein laboratory, pathology and imaging data, together with clinical information, are aggregated to support through expert systems, algorithms based on machine learning and artificial intelligence the provision to clinicians of a more actionable diagnostic information. Michael L. Wilson and Colleagues have suggested the need for integrating pathology and laboratory medicine services, thus creating the acronym PALM (pathology and laboratory medicine) (Wilson et al., 2019). A further integration which is receiving increasing interest and concern is that between clinical laboratories, pathology and radiology. In 2020, the European Society of Radiology (ESR) and the European Federation of Laboratory Medicine (EFLM) signed a memorandum of understanding confirming international support of integrative diagnostics (ID) between both disciplines (European Society of Radiology, n.d.). Lippi and Plebani, in a recently published paper, have emphasized that “better comprehension of several biological pathways, coupled with emerging technological advances, will

foster a paradigm shift in the way diagnostics has been for long acknowledged, paving the way to a new model of healthcare where integration of many different data will be more rapid, efficient and straightforward. This, in turn, may facilitate the acknowledgment, right interpretation and utilization of diagnostic information for an effective clinical reasoning and patient management” (Lippi and Plebani, 2020). Advanced information technology (IT) is needed for implementing ID and improving diagnostics. Innovative training models, new cultural and professional knowledge and skills are fundamental requisites for future laboratory professionals (Plebani et al., 2019).

REFERENCES

- 1. European Society of Radiology (no date):** ESR reaches out to clinical chemistry and laboratory medicine. Available at: <http://www.myesr.link/Mailings/esr@work-september-2019/>
- 2. Lippi, G., Plebani, M. (2020):** Integrated diagnostics: the future of laboratory medicine? *Biochem Med (Zagreb)* 2020; 30(1). doi: 10.11613/BM.2020.010501.
- 3. Plebani, M., Laposata, M., Lippi, G. (2019):** A manifesto for the future of laboratory medicine professionals. *Clin Chim Acta* 2019; 489:49-52. doi: 10.1016/j.cca.2018.11.021.
- 4. Wilson, M.L. et al. (2019):** The Lancet Commission on diagnostics: advancing equitable access to diagnostics. *Lancet* 2019; 393(10185):2018-2020. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(19)31052-9.